

- a. Existing house number
- b. Not existing house number
- c. New house number
- d. Removed house number
- e. Doubt house number (duplicate house number, wrong house number, etc.)

Fig. 2 Procedure of address geocoding

C. Check

There are two steps for checking house number information. If the correct ratio bellows 98% of each step, we need to re-investigation.

- a. Systematic check
 - 1. Quantity of house number and house number properties are correctness check: check the differences between existing house numbers and house registry numbers.
 - 2. Buildings and the corresponding spatial location check: One is check the building number and the corresponding street segment, the other one is check the spatial sequence of building numbers. House address must be the same as the road name (Fig.3), and the house number must also be consistent with the order (Fig.4).

Fig. 3 Check house number and road name (No.2 N.A. is wrong)

Fig. 4 Check house number sequence (No.3 E.A. is wrong)

- a. Spatial location check
 - Use a town as a unit, extracting 5% house numbers for on-site check.
 - 1. Check the house number's XY coordinates and its GPS coordinates
 - 2. Check the house number point within the building or not (Fig.5)

Fig. 5 Check the house number point

D. Build the database

Import data into GIS database under GIS data standard.

V. RESULT

According to the household registry list, total house number is 339,893. However, after field investigation, the real existing house number is 325,202 and the distribution is shown as Table I. There are four towns below 98% at the first check, and all reach the standard after the second check. All house numbers are built as database with GIS standard, and establish WebGIS for public services (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Interface of Kaoshiung City Address Webgis

VI. CONCLUSION

Nowadays, information of house number is very important for Location-Based Services (LBS) [4]. Like other Asian countries, street segments in Taiwan are chaotic, not regular. Hence, the field survey is indeed necessary. Based on the basic maps, people can check the correctness of household registry quickly. and also can through this study to re-check the quality and accuracy for house number information. To other Asian countries without address location spatial information system, the study can provide an effective way to build the address geocoding and establish a reliable GIS address database.

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